

PRÍJMY Z DANE Z NEHNUTEĽNOSTÍ A ICH MIESTO V DAŇOVÝCH PRÍJMOCH MIESTNYCH SAMOSPRÁV¹

REAL ESTATE TAX REVENUE AND IT'S PLACE IN LOCAL GOVERNMENT TAX REVENUE

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Abstrakt: Rozdielnosť prístupov k uplatňovaniu dane z nehnuteľností naprieč krajinami sveta dáva podnet k podrobnému sledovaniu určovania spôsobov výberu dane, určovania sadzieb dane a v konečnom dôsledku aj k sledovaniu vývoja príjmov z tejto dane v každej krajine samostatne. Príspevok sa zaoberá analyzovaním vývoja príjmov z dane z nehnuteľností v podmienkach slovenských samospráv so zreteľom na porovnanie obcí pod 100 obyvateľov a súvisiacich okresov v rámci sledovania podielov výnosu dane z nehnuteľností k výnosu celkových daňových príjmov a tempa rastu tohto podielu. Vývoj je v príspevku sledovaný analýzou údajov o príjmoch z analyzovanej dane slovenských samospráv z databázy Ministerstva financií SR podľa ekonomickej a funkčnej klasifikácie, za obdobie rokov 2005 až 2020.

Kľúčové slová: daň z nehnuteľností, miestne samosprávy, obce do 100 obyvateľov

Abstract: The diversity of approaches to the application of real estate tax across the countries of the world gives impetus to detailed monitoring of how the tax is levied, how the tax rates are set, and, ultimately, how the revenue from the tax evolves in each country separately. The paper deals with the analysis of the development of real estate tax revenue in the conditions of Slovak municipalities with regard to the comparison of municipalities under 100 inhabitants and related districts in terms of monitoring the shares of real estate tax revenue to the total tax revenue and the growth rate of this share. In the paper, the development is monitored using data on revenue of the analyzed tax of Slovak local governments from the database of the Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic according to economic and functional classification, covering the period from 2005 to 2020.

Key words: real estate tax, local governments, municipalities up to 100 inhabitants

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INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of the Slovak Republic, Act no. 582/2004 Coll. on local taxes and local fees for municipal waste and small construction waste, a group of local taxes, from which Slovak municipalities, right after share taxes, have the highest revenues. Local taxes and fees include real estate tax, dog tax, public land use tax, accommodation tax, vending machine tax, non-winning gaming machine tax, entry and residence tax for motor vehicles in historical parts of cities, nuclear equipment tax, local development fee and voluntary fee for municipal waste and small construction waste. Slovak legislation regulates the administration of real estate tax in Slovak municipalities, which in connection with the administration, compared to the Czech Republic, have greater powers, but also the costs that arise in the collection of tax (Sobotovičová, Janoušková, 2020). Real estate tax is an important part of municipal budget revenues due to its significant tax potential and the fact that real estate tax is the most important local tax of Slovak municipalities (Vartašová, Červená, 2022). The importance of local taxes, including real estate taxes, is also mentioned in Oates' Theory of Fiscal Federalism (1972).

The main goal of the paper is based on theoretical knowledge and data to quantify the share of real estate tax revenue to the total tax revenue of Slovak municipalities up to 100 inhabitants and the rate of its growth over time. This group of local governments, municipalities with less than 100 inhabitants according to the criteria from the last analyzed year, from 2020, was selected on the basis of its insufficient analysis in connection with real estate tax revenue and due to the topicality of insufficient revenue from this tax and efforts to increase them.

We achieved the goal of the paper through data on revenues of Slovak local governments from the database of the Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic according to economic and functional classification, based on the Act on free Access to Information, for the period 2005 – 2020. The analysis begins in 2005, as to be considered the year of implementation of fiscal decentralization in Slovakia (Maličká, 2019). The analysis ends in 2020 due to the unavailability of processed data (at the time of analysis) for the past year. In addition to income data, statistical data on the population from the database of the Statistical Office DATAcube were also used.

After filtering out municipalities with a population of less than 100, we proceeded to the calculation of the shares of real estate tax revenue to the revenue of total tax revenues and to monitor the growth rate of this share, to evaluate using

the method of descriptive statistics. In the analysis, we calculated the growth rate as the ratio of the absolute increase in the given period and the achieved level in the previous period.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Liptákov and Rigová (2019), monitoring the amount of income from local taxes, which also includes real estate tax, and analyzing their development is also important indicators in monitoring indicators of the financial and tax strength of municipalities and the self-financing rate. According to Malička (2021), the autonomy of local self-governments in Slovakia is closely connected with fiscal decentralization beginning in 2005, which is associated with the beginning of efforts to strengthen local governments' own revenues through the power to determine the amount of taxes collected (Balážová, Papcunová, Tej, 2016). Government-level decentralization of revenues has a positive effect on local tax revenues, which supports the effectiveness of fiscal decentralization, which has taken place in most European countries in recent decades (Maličká, Harčariková, Gazda, 2012). Vartašová and Červená (2021) emphasized that despite the importance of real estate tax revenues in the Slovak Republic, their analysis across the V4 countries showed that real estate tax is more important in Poland, with the greatest potential for legislation in this country, in which local governments have lower revenues from this tax.

According to Liptáková (2018), local taxes as such, flowing into the budgets of local governments, are only a theoretical way of decentralization of local governments in Slovakia due to the discrepancy between efforts and ensuring the highest possible tax revenues of local governments and maintaining a low burden on its inhabitants. The author considers a more universal tax - real estate tax, as one of the ways to cover expenses that even municipalities with a small population have. In connection with expenditures, the author Kriviņa (2019) deals with the hypothesis that the real estate tax has a relatively insignificant impact on the revenues of the municipal budget, but at the same time causes high administrative costs.

Despite the important position of this tax, its opponents can also be found in scientific circles. According to Kubánková (2010), real estate tax is unpopular due to the fact that real estate taxpayers do not earn primarily money and so there is no income from which they would pay real estate tax. The popularity of Prabhakar (2008), which speaks of the unfairness of double taxation, where

people pay income tax during an economically active period of life and subsequently in the post-productive part of life as part of a real estate tax, also speaks of unpopularity. The author believes that the real estate tax in this case is a recurring tax, which represents the taxation of their savings, which they gained during their economically active life. According to Sobotovičová and Janoškova (2020), the reluctance of local government residents to pay taxes, ie the essence of the unpopularity of real estate tax with taxpayers, is also based on a low degree of knowledge of the purpose of using revenues from this tax.

The method of real estate taxation in Slovakia is also a discussed issue. Vartašová and Červená (2021) identified, as one of the most serious problems of real estate taxation, the problem of not taking into account the real market value of real estate and the use of a small number of correction factors. The problem of taxation according to the market value of real estate was also emphasized by Achimovičová (2021), who claims that the system of taxation according to the market value of real estate is still unimplementable in Slovakia due to the absence of an effective mechanism for fair determination of the real market value of real estate. At the same time, the author emphasizes that the mentioned reform will be effective only in parallel with the reform of labor taxation.

In recent years, they have also highlighted the need to prepare fiscal measures that are effective during emergencies, including the COVID-19 pandemic. Molitoris (2021) states that some municipalities responded to the economic consequences of the pandemic by allowing real estate tax to be paid in three installments and by extending the payment deadline by up to one month for individuals. However, these were mostly self-governments of a larger nature than, for example, the capital of Slovakia - Bratislava.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF REAL ESTATE TAX REVENUE

From the above data on revenues of Slovak municipalities from the database of the Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic according to economic and functional classification, based on the Act on Free Access to Information, for the period 2005 to 2020, we decided to analyze municipalities with less than 100 inhabitants due to low degree of interest and monitoring the development of their tax revenues by the municipalities themselves, but by the state.

In the Fig. no. 1 you can see the division of these municipalities by districts on the map of the Slovak Republic. Districts with the darkest color have the most municipalities with a population of less than 100. The worst situation in relation

to such small municipalities is in the district of Svidník, where there are up to 22 such municipalities. As it can be seen, the municipalities are mostly in eastern Slovakia and in the south of central Slovakia in the border area. On the right side is a legend that explains the distribution of the number of municipalities across the districts of the Slovak Republic. In total, there are up to 35 such districts in Slovakia, together with 137 municipalities.

Fig. 1 Spatial representation of the number of municipalities with a population of less than 100

The largest number of districts shown on the map above is with one municipality with a population of less than 100. Among the districts with the highest number of municipalities according to the criterion of population of less than 100, Svidník also includes the district of Stropkov, Snina and Rimavská Sobota.

In connection with the average growth rate of the share of real estate tax revenue in total tax revenues, we also looked at the values of shares for individual districts separately. Fig no. 2 shows a graphical representation of the analyzed districts, which include the aforementioned 137 municipalities with a population of less than 100. The districts in which the municipalities with the highest average growth rates are located are the darkest in the graph in Figure 2. The maximum value of the average growth rate of these districts is 6.99 % in the district of

Banská Štiavnica. We identified the second fastest average growth rate in percentage in the Humenné district and the third fastest in the Gelnica district.

Among the districts and the slowest average growth rate - those districts in which the average values of growth did not increase but decreased, we can include the district of Žilina, Nové Mesto nad Váhom and the district of Košice-okolie based on the analysis. Throughout the analysis, we calculated the growth rate as the growth rate of the share of real estate tax revenues in total tax revenues. The share of real estate tax revenue to total tax revenues, its average growth rate, grew the fastest during the analyzed period in the districts of Banská Štiavnica, Gelnica and Humenné. On average, we recorded an average percentage decrease in the growth rate of the share in the 16th districts of Slovakia, in which there are municipalities with a population of less than 100.

Fig. 2 Spatial representation of the average growth rate in % of municipalities according to districts with a population of less than 100

The differences between the three districts with the fastest growth rate of the analyzed share and the three districts with the slowest growth, respectively with the decrease of the analyzed share, are also presented in the form of graphical visualization of data by quartiles. Fig. 3. shows the district of Banská Štiavnica, Gelnica, Humenné, Žilina, Nové Mesto nad Váhom and Košice-okolie, and as we mentioned, the first 3 districts are the districts with the fastest growth rate of the share of real estate tax revenue to total tax revenues, and conversely the last 3 districts are the districts with the slowest growth rate, respectively, with average decline values. Boxplots prove that the first 3 districts, the districts with the fastest growth rate of the analyzed share, have the highest maximum values and also the

highest average growth rate shown by points X. In the districts shown by the last three boxplots, average growth rates values, as well as the maximums are lower than in the districts with the fastest growth rate of the analyzed share. Outliers were also identified, shown by points outside the boxplots themselves.

Fig. 3 Graphical visualization of statistical differences between the three districts with the fastest growth rate of the share of real estate tax to the revenue of all tax revenues and the three districts with the slowest growth of this share

Due to the high number of Slovak municipalities with a low population, namely 137, we took a closer look only at the district with the largest number of small municipalities, the Svidník district itself, which has 22 municipalities with a population of less than 100. In Figure no. 4 we present a graphical representation of the average shares of real estate tax revenue to total tax revenues across municipalities in the Svidník district in aggregate in percentage terms for the period under review.

The graph shows that the average share during the analyzed 16-year period ranged between 19.9 % and 31.37 % of the investment, which means that on average, real estate tax revenues accounted for 19.9 % to 31.37 % of the total tax revenues of small municipalities in the Svidník district.

Fig. 4 Development of average shares of real estate tax revenue to total tax revenues across municipalities in the Svidnik district (in %, period 2005 – 2020)

DISCUSSION

Despite the importance of real estate tax revenues in the total tax revenues of small Slovak municipalities, the targeted increase in revenues is being discussed more and more by changing the method of taxation. However, this issue presents us with several problems. Despite the fact that our contribution does not address the problem in detail, we would like to point out that the effort to increase the tax burden on property taxes does not demotivate the people of Slovakia to the same extent as the burden of income tax. However, it is questionable whether taxation according to the market value of real estate can offset the three times high average real estate tax revenue of OECD countries. Especially for small municipalities, which we analyze in the article, after changing the method of taxation, it is possible that there will be a decrease in revenues, as the market value of real estate in areas with municipalities with a population of up to 100, compared to other areas of Slovakia, still low in the current period of the so-called "real estate post-covidy bubble".

The second problem of low tax revenues of small Slovak municipalities is also the problem of mini-participalization. Slovak municipalities have a constitutional (Article 66 of the Constitution of the Slovak Republic) the right to associate with other municipalities to ensure tasks of common interest, if the subject of their association is to achieve common goals and interests. Many small municipalities that we have analyzed are burdened by enforcement proceedings

or are under administration, and mergers can be a way for them to increase their tax revenues, including real estate tax revenue (Kováčová, 2014).

It is this research that has given us the opportunity to examine in detail the relationship between the level of property tax revenue, the number of inhabitants and, last but not least, the permeability of the state of compulsory administration.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the contribution showed more than a quarter of the average share of real estate tax revenues in the total tax revenues of Slovak municipalities with less than 100 inhabitants. The paper identified up to 35 districts with 137 municipalities with a population of less than 100. The number of districts with municipalities with a population of less than 100 is almost at the level of almost half of all districts in Slovakia (79).

Analysis of data on revenues of Slovak municipalities from the database of the Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic according to economic and functional classification, based on the Act on Free Access to Information, for the period 2005 to 2020, showed that the maximum value of the average growth rate of real estate tax revenue to total tax revenues, was identified in the districts - Banská Štiavnica, Humenné and Gelnica. Among the districts and the slowest average growth rate, among those districts in which the average growth values of the analyzed share were identified as negative, we can include the district of Žilina, Nové Mesto nad Váhom and the district of Košice-okolie on the basis of the analysis

In the last part of the analysis, we focused on the district with the largest number of municipalities with a population of less than 100, namely the district of Svidník. There are 22 municipalities in the Svidník district assessed by the above-mentioned criteria. The analysis showed that the average growth rate of the share of real estate tax revenue to total tax revenues is a 5.55 % year-on-year increase.

Based on the analysis, other questions arise for research, which would specify the reasons for the low average year-on-year growth rate of real estate tax revenues (0.76 %) despite the substantial share of these revenues in total tax revenues of Slovak municipalities (1/4).

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